

Enhancing reliability-based design optimization through adaptive Kriging and gradient-free optimization

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Abstract

Optimizing complex systems in large-scale applications requires fulfilling specifications and accommodating uncertainties. Traditional constrained optimization frameworks can be time-consuming, especially when evaluating rare event probabilities. This study introduces a novel strategy that integrates Adaptive Kriging (AK) and Evolutionary Algorithms (EA) for efficient Reliability-Based Design Optimization (RBDO). Kriging models approximate limit state functions and are iteratively updated, focusing on optimal design parameters and constraints. We compare two methods: one using an evolutionary algorithm for global optimization and the other targeting cost-effective search areas based on iso-cost regions. The latter refines the accuracy of the surrogate model locally, avoids unnecessary enrichments, and explores multiple local minima. In this study, we evaluate these algorithms' effectiveness using engineering benchmarks.

1 Introduction

1.1 General considerations

Optimizing complex systems in large-scale applications is critical since structural design must fulfill various engineering specifications while accommodating inherent uncertainties. The application of constrained optimization frameworks has proven their effectiveness in addressing these requirements by incorporating uncertainties as constraints. However, this approach often becomes extremely time-consuming when assessing the probabilities associated with rare events [1]. A possible strategy is reducing the need to evaluate failure probabilities, reducing computational complexity, and enhancing overall performance. Reliability-Based Design Optimization (RBDO) has evidenced considerable focus on exploiting metamodel-assisted approaches to mitigate computational burden using inexpensive surrogates. Despite these advancements, a significant challenge remains: reducing the number of failure probability assessments to limit mechanical model calculations. Our research aims to address this critical issue.

1.2 Motivation and objective

This study presents a new method that merges Adaptive Kriging (AK) and Evolutionary Algorithms (EA) to efficiently tackle RBDO problems via Monte Carlo simulation-based reliability assessment. The use of gradient-free methods is particularly useful in computational simulations where gradient calculation is time-consuming, impractical, or prone to failure, providing robustness, adaptability, and versatility. The methodology leverages the Kriging surrogate model to approximate limit state functions (LSFs) expanded in an augmented domain to determine the feasibility of Monte Carlo samples. The adaptive enrichment strategy proposed enables parallel reliability computation and optimization. We compare two approaches: one using an EA for global optimization and the other targeting cost-effective search areas based on iso-cost regions. In this study, engineering benchmarks validate the effectiveness of these approaches, demonstrating the proposed algorithm's performance capabilities and reinforcing its reliability.

2 Background

2.1 Literature context on RBDO methodologies

Reliability-Based Design Optimization aims to optimize system performance while ensuring a specific reliability level [2]. This field has seen a significant increase in contributions in recent years, with the development of various methods, including two-level, mono-level, decoupled, and metamodel approaches, as well as approximation-based and simulation-based reliability analysis techniques [3, 4, 5]. In the most popular two-level method, the system failure probability is estimated using techniques like FORM or SORM, and then the optimization runs to find the best design parameters. Although efficient, these methods may not always be accurate for complex systems, prompting the use of advanced reliability methods such as Monte Carlo simulation and Subset Simulation to improve results [6, 7].

Recent literature has highlighted the effective use of metamodel-assisted approaches to improve RBDO performance. These methods reduce the computational cost of complex engineering models by using inexpensive surrogates [8]. Several Kriging-assisted approaches have been proposed for nested-loop RBDO problems, replacing time-consuming limit-state functions with Kriging models [9, 10, 11]. Kriging is favored in RBDO for its high accuracy in modeling relationships between system inputs and outputs and providing probabilistic estimates of system responses for reliability evaluation. It is adept at handling deterministic and stochastic inputs and modeling non-linear input-output relationships.

Moreover, meta-heuristic algorithms like genetic algorithms and particle swarm optimization have garnered attention in RBDO for their ability to navigate intricate design spaces and non-linear objectives, mainly when gradient information is not available or challenging to compute. Recent research increasingly focuses on combining Kriging with gradient-free optimization algorithms to enhance RBDO for various engineering systems [12, 13, 14]. While these methods offer probabilistic estimates of system responses, they are often computationally intensive, limiting their suitability for large-scale optimization problems. Therefore, further research is needed to develop more efficient and effective RBDO methods.

2.2 RBDO problem formulation

The general formulation of an RBDO problem reads as follows (see, e.g., [2]):

$$\mathbf{d}^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{d} \in \mathcal{D}} c(\mathbf{d}) \quad \text{subject to:} \quad \begin{cases} f_j(\mathbf{d}) \leq 0, & \{j = 1, \dots, n_s\}, \\ \mathbb{P}(\mathbf{g}_k(\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{d}), \mathbf{Z}) \leq 0) \leq \bar{\mathcal{P}}_{f_k}, & \{k = 1, \dots, n_h\}. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In this equation, the cost function $c(\mathbf{d})$ must be minimized with respect to the unknown design variables $\mathbf{d} = \{d_1, \dots, d_{n_d}\} \in \mathbb{D}_{\mathbf{d}} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_d}$ to meet the system's soft and hard constraints. The first are simple functions that bound the design space; the second are limit-state functions that describe the system's performance. The system's failure occurs when the limit-state functions $\mathbf{g}_k(\mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{d}}, \mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{p}}) \leq 0$. The probabilistic constraint $\mathbb{P}(\mathbf{g}_k(\mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{d}}, \mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{p}}) \leq 0)$ must not exceed a fixed threshold probability $\bar{\mathcal{P}}_{f_k}$ (e.g., from 10^{-2} to 10^{-8} for rare event estimation).

The following integral gives the computational definition of the failure probability:

$$P_{f_k} = \mathbb{P}(\mathbf{g}_k(\mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{d}}, \mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{p}}) \leq 0) = \int_{\mathbb{F} = \{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{X} : \mathbf{g}_k(\mathbf{x}) \leq 0\}} f_{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x}, \quad (2)$$

$\mathbb{F} = \{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{X} : \mathbf{g}_k(\mathbf{x}) \leq 0\}$ is the failure domain and $\mathbb{X} = \{\mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{d}}, \mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{p}}\}$ is the vector of the random variables. The random variables are comprised of $\mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{d}} \sim f_{\mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{d}}|\mathbf{d}} : \mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{d}} = \{x_{d,1}, \dots, x_{d,n_d}\}$, which depend on the design variables \mathbf{d} , and $\mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{p}} \sim f_{\mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{p}}|\mathbf{p}} : \mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{p}} = \{x_{p,1}, \dots, x_{p,n_p}\}$, which are other random variables of the underlying problem that do not depend on the design variables.

3 Methodology

3.1 Surrogate-assisted approach with zero-order optimization algorithm

Solving Equation (1) usually requires numerous evaluations of the performance function g_k . In surrogate-assisted RBDO, the original model g_k is replaced with a faster and more efficient surrogate model \hat{g}_k to reduce computational costs. The Kriging models are iteratively updated according to a chosen learning function. Specifically in this study, the U learning function defined in [15] as $U = |\mu_{\hat{g}}|/\sigma_{\hat{g}}$ is employed, where $\mu_{\hat{g}}$ and $\sigma_{\hat{g}}$ represent the Kriging mean prediction and variance of the limit state function g_k , respectively. This work delves into the comparative analysis of two distinct approaches presented in Section 3.2 and 3.3, respectively. The first approach employs an evolutionary algorithm to search for global optimal design parameters that satisfy reliability constraints. It operates directly on the design space, and the chosen EA detects the most interesting region to seek the optimal solution. On the other hand, the second approach identifies cost-effective areas to search for the optimal solution based on iso-cost regions. This notion, a novel introduction to the RBDO framework, allows for confining the search to a subset of the original design space characterized by specific activated cost levels. In both strategies, the evolution starts with random design individuals, serving both in optimization and in the initial DoE. The adaptive enrichment strategy is directed towards regions likely to encompass optimal design parameters proximal to the imposed constraints. It occurs concurrently with optimization, ensuring parallel operation of reliability computation and optimization. The procedure iterates until the stopping conditions for reliability and solution optimality are satisfactorily met.

3.2 Global search strategy

The global search strategy uses a Genetic Algorithm (GA) operating directly in the design space \mathcal{D} to search for optimal global design parameters that meet the reliability constraints. The adaptive enrichment is directed towards regions likely to encompass optimal design parameters proximal to the imposed constraints employing an active learning (AL) metric. This metric gathers information from the optimization process and the metamodel parameters, specifically the Kriging mean and variance. Consequently, the metamodel is adaptively and efficiently enriched only in critical regions where the optimal design parameters are likely to be found. The evolution begins with randomly generated design individuals. The latter is also selected as the initial DoE to compute the global Kriging and classify whether a design solution belongs to the feasible region. At each iteration, a new generation is constructed starting from the previous one using the normalized fitness function f of Equation (3) that also represents the new solution set for the next algorithm iteration:

$$f(\mathbf{X}_d) = \frac{c^*(\mathbf{d}) + \mathbb{I}[\mathbb{P}(\hat{g}(\mathbf{X}_d) \leq 0) \leq \bar{\mathcal{P}}_{f_k}]}{2} \quad \text{where : } \begin{cases} \mathbb{I} = 0 & \hat{g}(\mathbf{X}_d) > 0 \\ \mathbb{I} = 1 & \hat{g}(\mathbf{X}_d) \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$c^*(\mathbf{d})$ is the normalized cost, whereas \mathbb{I} expresses the indicator factor used to identify the sign of the reliability constraint, i.e., whether a design realization is feasible or not. If necessary, an enrichment is performed simultaneously with the optimization to gradually improve the metamodel's accuracy. This task targets areas where probabilistic constraints might be violated and near the reliable optimum. The new Active Learning metric is defined, adding a candidate sample \mathbf{x}^{new} to the DoE as follows:

$$\mathbf{x}^{\text{new}} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{X}} U(\mathbf{X}^{\text{best}}(\mathbf{d}^{(i-\text{gen})})) \quad (4)$$

The hard constraint is checked at each step estimating the failure probability by using the MCS and the Kriging model sequentially enriched. The algorithm loops until the stop condition associated with the solution's optimality is reached, i.e., when the number of generations reaches the given maximum number.

3.3 Iso-cost region strategy

The iso-cost region strategy enhances RBDO efficiency by reducing computational load focusing on cost-effective regions. If necessary, the initial DoE is locally updated by selecting points from the iso-cost levels according to a chosen learning function. If no feasible solutions exist within the iso-cost levels, the algorithm adapts them accordingly, allowing exploration of new regions. The search is restricted to specific activated cost levels of the design space. This targeted approach helps refine the accuracy of the surrogate model on a local scale, limiting enrichments only to relevant areas close to the optimal cost. Consequently, this mitigates unnecessary metamodel enrichments in areas associated with higher costs while simultaneously facilitating the exploration of multiple local minima. Specifically, a new parameter $\alpha := Q_\alpha(\mathbf{d}; \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{d}))$ is set to explore progressively the design domain \mathcal{D} through cost-activated smaller region \mathcal{D}_α . Therefore, Equation (1) is modified as follows:

$$\mathbf{d}^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{d} \in \mathcal{D}_\alpha \subset \mathcal{D}} \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{d}) \quad \text{subject to:} \quad \begin{cases} f_j(\mathbf{d}) \leq 0, & \{j = 1, \dots, n_s\}, \\ \mathbb{P}(\mathbf{g}_k(\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{d}), \mathbf{Z}) \leq 0) \leq \bar{\mathcal{P}}_{f_k}, & \{k = 1, \dots, n_h\}. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

It is worth noting that the considerations discussed in Section 3.2 also apply to this approach. The outline of the algorithm reads as follows:

Algorithm 1 - Outline

- 1: Generate the initial random population: $\mathbf{d}^{(0-gen)} = \{d_1, \dots, d_{n_d}\}$
 - 2: Build the Kriging surrogate $\hat{\mathbf{g}}_k^{(0)}(\mathbf{X}_d)$ of the limit state function on $\mathbf{d}^{(0-gen)}$
 - 3: Select initial α_q from the set of the cost quantiles $\alpha_q \in [\underline{\alpha}, \bar{\alpha}]$, $q = \{1, \dots, M_q\}$
 - 4: increment $\alpha = \text{True}$
 - 5: **while** increment α **do**
 - 6: **while** $n^{(i-gen)} \leq n^{(MAX-gen)}$ **do**
 - 7: **for each** $d_m \in \mathbf{d}^{(i-gen)} \subset \mathcal{D}_{\alpha_q}$ **do** sampling local Monte Carlo population
 - 8: Compute $\hat{P}_{f_k} = \mathbb{P}(\hat{\mathbf{g}}_k(\mathbf{X}_d) \leq 0) = \frac{N_{\hat{\mathbf{g}} \leq 0}}{N_{MCS}}$
 - 9: **end for**
 - 10: Evaluation of the fitness function $f(\mathbf{X}_d)$ defined in Equation (3)
 - 11: Selection $n_d/2$ parent pairs from for crossover
 - 12: Generate a new population of n_d offspring
 - 13: Randomly mutate some points in the population to obtain $\mathbf{d}^{(i+1-gen)}$
 - 14: **if** $U(\mathbf{X}^{best}(\mathbf{d}^{(i+1-gen)})) < 2$ **then** $\mathbf{x}^{new} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{X}} U(\mathbf{X}^{best}(\mathbf{d}^{(i-gen)}))$
 - 15: DoE $^{(i+1-gen)}_+ = \mathbf{x}^{new}$
 - 16: Update Kriging surrogate $\hat{\mathbf{g}}_k^{(s)}(\mathbf{X}_d)$ on DoE $^{(i+1-gen)}$
 - 17: **else**
 - 18: **if** $d_{best}^{(i-gen)}$ is Feasible **then** increment $\alpha = \text{False}$
 - 19: **end if**
 - 20: **end if**
 - 21: $n^{(i-gen)}_+ = 1$
 - 22: **end while**
 - 23: **end while**
-

By excluding the parameter α from the above outline, we can obtain the global search strategy as well.

4 Numerical benchmark

4.1 Four-branch function

This section investigates the 2-dimensional four-branch function to compare the strategies illustrated in Section 3. The four-branch function (see Figure 1 (a)) is a common benchmark problem in RBDO (see, e.g., [16, 15, 17]). The function describes the failure of a series system with four distinct limit state components. The mathematical formulation of the four-branch function reads:

$$f(\mathbf{X}_d, p) = \min \begin{cases} 3 + 0.1(x_1 - x_2)^2 - \frac{x_1+x_2}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 3 + 0.1(x_1 - x_2)^2 + \frac{x_1+x_2}{\sqrt{2}} \\ (x_1 - x_2) + \frac{p}{\sqrt{2}} \\ (x_2 - x_1) + \frac{p}{\sqrt{2}} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The input variables $\mathbf{X}_d = \{x_1, x_2\}$ are modeled as two Gaussian random variables: $x_1 \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_1, 0.1)$; $x_2 \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_2, 0.1)$, and p is a constant parameter having value 6. The design vector $\mathbf{d} = \{\mu_1, \mu_2\}$ is a set of parameters restrained in the following hyperrectangular design space:

$$\mathbb{D}_d = [-6; 6] \times [-6; 6] \subset \mathbb{R}^2 \quad (7)$$

The optimization is performed to minimize the eggholder objective function:

$$c(\mathbf{d}) = -(\mu_2 + 47) \sin \left(\sqrt{\left| \mu_2 + \frac{\mu_1}{2} + 47 \right|} \right) - \mu_1 \sin \left(\sqrt{\left| \mu_1 - (\mu_2 + 47) \right|} \right) \quad (8)$$

Table 1 summarizes all the parameters used to set the algorithm options.

Table 1: Set of algorithm's parameters used in the numerical benchmark.

Parameters	Symbol	Value
Maximum number of generation	$n^{(MAX-gen)}$	200
Number of chromosomes in each population	n_{chr}	32
Crossover probability	p_c	0.7
Mutation probability	p_m	0.1
Number of samples of the input vector in each population	N_{MCS}	10^5
Threshold probability	\overline{P}_{f_k}	10^{-3}

4.2 Results

Figure 1 (b) and (c) pictures the algorithm at convergence for the global search and iso-cost region strategies, respectively. In the plots, the dashed line represents the prediction of the Kriging mean, and the yellow circles with grey crosses represent the enrichment points added to the original DoE (grey crosses in the plots). In contrast, the green crosses surrounded by the purple nebula are the design solutions, with their local Monte Carlo population generated during the optimization phase. The Kriging surrogate prediction is more accurate near the optimal solution at the final stage of the algorithms. This is because most enrichment is performed in that region for both strategies. Additionally, the superposition of all the chromosomes in the final frame demonstrates that the algorithm has achieved convergence. The two algorithms show distinct behaviors during the enrichment steps. In particular, the global strategy allocates more computational resources to areas where the surrogate is uncertain, even if they are not cost-relevant. Conversely, the iso-cost strategy focuses only on adding points with minimum cost in the activated cost islands.

Figure 1: (a) four-branch reference function; (b) surrogate prediction and solution at convergence (global search strategy); (c) surrogate prediction and solution at convergence (iso-cost region strategy).

To evaluate the statistical variability in the results, 50 simulations are performed with different initial random seeds. The performance of the proposed strategies is presented in Table 2. Figure 2 represents the comparison between the two algorithms based on three different metrics: cost value, model evaluations, and the value of the design parameters (d_1^* and d_2^*). The first plot (a) shows that both algorithms achieve similar median cost values, but the global search strategy exhibits lower variability, indicating more consistent performance in terms of cost. While having a comparable median, the iso-cost region strategy shows higher variability in the cost values, suggesting less consistency but a better absolute cost value. Regarding model evaluations, the global strategy generally requires more evaluations, with a median of 25, compared to the iso-cost strategy's 21. This suggests that the global strategy is more computationally intensive. The algorithm's range of model evaluations is broader, indicating it may explore the design space more extensively, even when not strictly necessary. Regarding the design parameters (d_1^* and d_2^*), the global strategy shows more variability. This may indicate a more thorough search for the optimal solution. Conversely, the iso-cost strategy demonstrates less variability, with narrower ranges for both d_1^* and d_2^* , suggesting a more focused search within specific regions.

Table 2: Comparative results in terms of calls to the performance function for the numerical example.

Method	μ_1	μ_2	\mathbf{c}	\mathbf{g}_1 -calls
Global search strategy	-3.15	-0.51	-60.15	25
Iso-cost region strategy	-3.00	-0.63	-60.45	21

Overall, the global strategy shows strengths in achieving consistent cost values and thoroughly exploring the design space, albeit with higher computational demands. While less consistent in cost values, the iso-cost strategy is more computationally efficient and demonstrates a focused approach in the search for optimal design parameters.

5 Conclusions

This work introduces a novel enrichment strategy that integrates Adaptive Kriging (AK) and Evolutionary Algorithms (EA) for Reliability-Based Design Optimization (RBDO). This approach leverages metamodel-assisted RBDO to enhance computational efficiency, particularly with Monte Carlo simulation-based reliability assessments. By iteratively updating Kriging surrogate models, the method effectively classifies Monte Carlo samples and focuses on regions likely to contain optimal design parameters and constraints.

The proposed strategy demonstrates adaptability through gradient-free methods, which are especially beneficial in computational simulations where gradient calculations are impractical or time-consuming. This

Figure 2: (a) cost value; (b) model evaluations; (c) design solution.

study compares two approaches: the global search strategy, which explores the entire design space but is resource-intensive, and the iso-cost search approach, which targets cost-effective regions subset of the original design space with activated cost levels. The latter refines the surrogate model's accuracy locally and avoids unnecessary metamodel enrichments in high-cost areas. This facilitates the exploration of multiple local minima and reduces the computational load.

Benchmark tests confirm that this strategy significantly reduces computational load and improves the efficiency of RBDO processes by limiting unnecessary metamodel enrichments. The findings indicate a substantial enhancement in refining Kriging surrogates around the most reliable design solutions within an affordable computational cost.

Future research will extend this metric to handle more complex problems and high-dimensional input spaces to provide a probabilistic estimate of system responses. Continued development and refinement of these methods will further improve their efficiency and effectiveness in RBDO applications.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 955393.

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